

TECHNO-EQUIPPED EDUCATION: A CRITICAL OVERVIEW

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Abstract :

As of late, there has been far-reaching enthusiasm around the potential for innovation to change learning. As interests in technology for education keep on developing, students, parents, and instructors face an apparently perpetual cluster of training advancements from which to look over customized learning stages from instructive games to online courses. In the midst of the fervor, it is vital to venture back and see how techno-based education can help-or now and again deter the students' learning. Techno-based education has altered the traditional concept of education. The significance of techno-based education can't be disregarded. In reality, with the introduction of computers in education, it has become more straightforward for teachers to impart knowledge to the students. The utilization of techno-based education has made the method of teaching and learning even more lively. This paper talks about the competence of techno-based methodologies in education and provides prospective areas of research in this direction.

Key words: *Education, technology, teaching, learning*

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Introduction :

The commonly viewed epoch of technological advancements is the age of the 21st century. At present, technology has become an internal part of our lives. It is viewed as a premise of economic development. An economy without technological advancements can never develop in the present situation. This is on the grounds that technology makes our work a lot simpler and less tedious. The effect of technology can be seen in each imaginable field and one such area is education.

Use & Importance of Technology in Education :

As per the most recent information with respect to how precisely the students really like to utilize technology in education and how their learning gets affected while using the technology, it was found that with the use of technical devices, the learning and intuitiveness of the learners have grown. They additionally think that it becomes considerably more collaborative, just as filled with exciting fields when education is equipped with technology. The exchange of information turns out to be extremely simple and advantageous, just as persuasive. This means, our mind works quicker with the utilization of technology in education, be it any piece of life, here we discuss techno-based education.

The need and support of such advancement, which basically makes the teaching and learning process a simple, smooth endeavor is totally unavoidable currently even in schools, colleges and universities.

Techno-based education is four-dimensional: it is incorporated as a section of the educational plan, as an informative framework, for the purpose of supporting teaching-learning, and furthermore as an instrument to develop the whole learning process. It is due to the techno-based education teaching and learning has been developed from inactive and receptive to collaborative and lively.

Teaching and learning are very fundamental in every walk of life irrespective of the different areas. Previously, people were educated to do things in any other way than they did earlier. Now, education is used as a means to make the learners curious about the world around them. Regardless, the utilization of techno-based education can help students comprehend and remember ideas better. Students can enjoy and use techno-based education in the following manner:

Internet Connection :

The internet has become significant many times over the period of more than a decade now. Its significance in academics can now never be underestimated. Apart from the use of the internet for crimes and other unnecessary things, its use in education is beneficial for students. At present, the internet is used for everything from TV to gaming consoles, and our telephones, the internet is in a real sense all over the place. The utilization of the internet allows the students to have ease of access to all sorts of instructional exercises and different types of helping material that could be used for educational development and learning enhancement.

Use of Visuals :

Visual pictures generally have a solid attraction as opposed to words. Making use of visuals to enhance learning is an effective way of techno-based education. Many academic institutions at present depend on the utilization of astounding visual introductions and visual projections to make learning intuitive and intriguing. The use of technical devices, for example, projectors in the classrooms can increase the understanding level of the students effectively. Students like to see engaging visuals and something that attracts them to develop thinking rather than merely reading the words on a white page. The use of techno-based methods of teaching and learning in education makes the process very interesting through the use of visuals.

Blessing of Techno-Based education: Online Courses :

With the use of technology, online courses have currently been turned into exceptionally normal activities. Anyone who wishes to take up internet-based courses for his/her learning can easily find different courses on the online platforms at a distance of a few clicks. Well-known academic institutions offer astounding online courses with the utilization of different techno-based applications and the internet. This is the notion that will keep on growing as it gets more assistance and consciousness. Internet-based courses all over the world are more popular amongst students who work and search for adjustable educational opportunities based on technology.

Affecting Factors in Techno-based Education :

Jung points out the huge challenges that teachers are facing as a result of the quick expansion of knowledge. Modern technology has become a challenge for teachers as they have to incorporate it into their teaching. Along with the development of the technology, there is a need for teacher training in order to make the teachers aware of the technology. Gressard and Loyd affirmed that teachers' mentality towards technology is a vital factor in the effective execution of techno-based education. They brought up the issue that teachers do not consistently have an optimistic view towards technology and their distrustful approaches might result in the failure of the techno-based teaching-learning process.

The most commonly cited reasons towards techno-based education are:

- lack of time to upgrade their knowledge about technology;
- lack of access to the technical devices;
- lack of resources to make technology available;
- lack of support from authorities.

Positive Points of Techno-Based Education :

Improved Teaching and Learning :

Techno-based education makes use of various devices like digital cameras, projectors, different learning software, computer applications, PowerPoint presentations, and visuals. These have become extraordinary sources for teachers to assist students with getting hands-on experience without any problem. It must be perceived that visual clarification of ideas makes learning fun for students. They are ready to contribute more in the class and even teachers get an opportunity to make their teaching more collaborative and attractive.

Global Access :

Techno-based education makes it possible for students in different parts of the world to meet students from other regions through video conferencing without leaving the classroom. Some sites are useful for students to learn different foreign languages online by forming groups of students and teachers from other countries.

Negative Issues of Techno-Based Education :

The Problem of Developing Writing Skills :

Because of the unnecessary use of chatting and emoticons, the composing abilities of the students have been harmed to a greater extent. Nowadays, students depend largely on computerized correspondence that they have completely ignored developing their writing skills. They forgot the spellings of various words, how to utilize sentence structure appropriately or how to develop beautiful handwriting.

The Issue of Cheating :

Technological advancements like graphical calculators, smartwatches, spy cameras, and digital devices have become extraordinary sources of malpractices in examinations. It has become very easy for the students to make use of technology for the wrong purposes.

The Problem of Concentration on Academic Work :

Technical devices have become a favorite pastime for students. Every now and then students use their smartphones, tablets, and laptops for other reasons than study. Being in touch with everyone online, students' concentration abilities have declined to a greater extent. With the introduction of technology at an early age, students have forgotten the importance of sports and physical fitness.

Conclusion :

Technology affects teaching-learning and simultaneously may likewise present adverse consequences. Teachers and students should make use of technology for their betterment. The negative issues can be dealt with authoritatively by the elders while allowing students access to technology. Techno-based education can prove fruitful if and when it is used in an effective way. Thus, it can be concluded that techno-based education has both good and bad results, It depends on the users of the technology in education to make worth of it.

References :

1. Beringer, V. (2009, October 20) For kids, pen's mightier than keyboard. *futurity.org*. Retrieved February 25th 2013 from <http://www.futurity.org/society-culture/for-kids-pens-mightier-than-keyboard/#more-4909>.
2. Bransford, J., Brown, A., & Cocking, R. (2000). *How people learn: Brain, mind, experience, and school*. Washington, DC: National Academic Press.
3. Brill, J. M., & Galloway, C. (2007). Perils and promises: University instructors' integration of technology in classroom-based practices. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. 38(1), 95-105.
4. Leising, J. (2013 January 30) The new script for teaching handwriting is no script at all. *wsj.com* Retrieved February 25th 2013 from <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424127887323644904578272151551627948.html?KEYWORDS=handwriting>
5. Roschelle, J., Pea, R., Hoadley, C., Gordin, D., & Means, B. (2000). *Future of children*, 10(2), 76-101.
6. Wenglinski, H. (1998). *Does it compute? The relationship between educational technology and student achievement in mathematics*. Princeton, NJ: ETS.

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